

The Effectiveness of Math Apps-Aided Instructions in Improving Mathematical Skills at Manggahan Elementary School

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 04 June 2024; **Accepted:** 04 July 2024; **Published:** 07 Aug 2024

Abstract: This study on improving mathematical skills using Math apps-aided instructions employed the quasi-experimental two-group-pretest-posttest design method of research. It was conducted using 20 control group and 20 experimental group for the school year 2021-2022 at Manggahan Elementary School. These participants were chosen purposively since the availability of the resources for the participants was considered in the section of the experimental group.

It was revealed in the findings of the study that both classes' mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns was higher than the pre-test results by using Math Apps Aided Instruction for the experimental class and the conventional method for the controlled class. The experimental class's mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns are the same as the control class. Moreover, when Math Apps Aided Instruction is used, the experimental subjects' mathematical abilities in terms of number sense, fundamental operations, problem solving, and mathematical patterns significantly improve. That there is a significant difference in scores exists between students taught using Math Apps Aided Instructions and those taught using the conventional method.

Finally, that Math Apps-Aided Instructions is more effective than the conventional method of instruction; consequently, Math Apps-Aided Instructions significantly improves participants' mathematical abilities in terms of number sense, basic operations, problem solving, and mathematical patterns.

Keywords: Math, Instruction, Effectiveness, Skills, Problem Solving, Basic Operations.

Introduction

People must be masters of basic math abilities due to the ever-changing needs of society since the pandemic, the quantitative boom, and the increased availability and desire for technologies such as computers and calculators. There are several areas of math abilities that every student should acquire in addition to the most fundamental of all math skills, add-subtract-multiply-divide. To help pupils overcome their obstacles, teachers should use several methods of teaching mathematics, such as the drill method, various audio visual aids, and computer aided education.

According to Chen (2017), computer-assisted instruction has been proved to improve students' academic achievement. Computer-assisted education was a viable teaching method since it could improve students'

academic performance as well as their learning interests and attitudes.

Mathematics and computers are both crucial in today's world since they open the door to a plethora of opportunities. Mathematics is commonly employed in both hardware and software in computers. The success of Math-Apps Aidedteaching in learning is inextricably linked to the usage of multimedia, which was created in steps that included needs analysis, learning design development, expert validation, and rigorous testing. The various processes resulted in multimedia that is suited for learning. Students can express themselves in a variety of ways about a variety of mathematical topics. Based on a tutorial model that requires students to grasp the mathematical ideas gained before going on to more challenging concepts, the proposed system was able to develop a self-regulated learning model and generate comprehensive learning habits. If students are taught mathematical topics in a systematic and organized manner, they will learn them more readily and thoroughly (Umbara et.al., 2020).

In Math-Apps Aidedinstruction, the teacher's role as a facilitator is extremely vital in assisting students in finding mathematical ideas through a two-way communication process. If ICT learning is characterized by reactive supervision, it has the potential to degrade learning by overriding interactions that are guided directly by the instructor in a pedagogic manner, hence ICT use in learning should be done with teacher supervision and guidance (Munir, Kusnendar, & Rahmadhani, 2016).

Consequently, this study determined the effectiveness of the used of math-apps aided instruction in improving the Mathematical skills of the pupils.

Statement of the Problem

The main problem of the study determined the effectiveness of Math-Apps Aidedinstruction in improving the mathematical skills of the pupils at Manggahan Elementary School. The specific problems that this study aimed to answer the following;

1. What is the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group and the control group in terms of the following Mathematical skills;
 - 1.1. Number sense
 - 1.2. Basic operation
 - 1.3. Problem solving
 - 1.4. Mathematical Pattern
2. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of the experimental group and the control group in terms of their Mathematical skills?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group and the control group in terms of their Mathematical skills?
4. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the experimental group and the control group in terms of their Mathematical skills?
5. What are the learning gains of each group?
6. How effective is the use of Math Apps-Aided Instruction in improving the mathematical skills of the participants?

Statement of Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the experimental group and the control group in terms of their Mathematical skills.
2. There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group and the control group in terms of their Mathematical skills.
3. There is no significant difference between the posttest scores of the experimental group and the control

group in terms of their Mathematical skills.

Methods

Research Design

This investigation utilized a quasi-experimental two-group pre- and post-test design. The definition of experimental research is an experiment in which the researcher manipulates one variable and controls or randomizes the remaining variables. There is a control group, random assignment of subjects to groups, and the researcher tests only one effect at a time. Additionally, it is essential to know which variables must be tested and measured. It is research in which the independent variable is manipulated by the researcher. The researcher attempts to maintain control over all variables that may influence the outcome of an experiment. The researcher attempts to determine or predict potential outcomes in this manner. Two-group experimental design is defined as an experimental design with a treatment group and a control group (non-treatment group). This is one of the simplest experimental designs ever created. In design notation, groups were assigned at random. One group receives the treatment or program, while the other group, the comparison group, does not.

Research Population and Sampling

The study was conducted using 20 pupils under control group and 20 pupils under experimental group for the school year 2021-2022 at Manggahan Elementary School. Those participants were chosen purposively since the availability of the resources for the participants was considered in the selection of the experimental group. The study was limited on the profile of the respondents such as the gender and age; the performance of the pupils in terms of the following mathematical skills such as number sense, basic operation, problem solving, and mathematical patterns in the study; the pre test scores of control and experimental group; the post test scores of the control and experimental group; and significant difference between the pretest and post test scores of the two groups in determining the effectivity of the used of computer-aided instruction in improving Mathematical skills.

Research Environment

The forty-room Manggahan Elementary School was chosen by the researcher. The classrooms are standard rooms, meaning they adhere to DepEd's safety and usability standards. Due to an abundance of students from the surrounding area, thirty classrooms are utilized for instruction. The location of the study is also where the researcher works as an elementary school educator. The school provides an environment conducive to research, as evidenced by its consistently excellent performance in external research audits. Using a variety of strategies, the school intends to preserve and enhance its long-standing success.

Each faculty's research environment is designed to support the needs of the disciplines within that faculty. The manner in which research is conducted in various disciplines within a faculty influences the organization of research activities, the support for research students, and the administration of research degree programs.

Research Instrumentation

In this study, the researcher uses a teacher-made test as an instrument, applying a set of tests: Pretest and Post-test. The teacher-made test consisted of 30 test items using multiple choice with four choices, a, b, c and d. To ensure the integrity of the pre-test and post-test results, both tests had the same content but differed only in ordering test items.

The questionnaire considered the learning competencies on finding ratio and proportion; expressing one value as a fraction of another given their ratio and vice versa; defining and illustrating the meaning of ratio and proportion using or pictorial models; setting up proportions for groups and for given situations; finding a missing term in a proportion; solving problems involving direct proportion, partitive proportion, and inverse proportion in different contexts as distance, rate, and time using appropriate strategies and tools; creating problems involving ratio and proportion with reasonable answers; finding the percentage

or rate or percent in a given problem, solving routine and non-routine problems involving finding the percentage, rate and base using appropriate strategies and tools; solving percent problems such as percent of increase/decrease commission, sale tax, and simple interest; creating problems involving percent, with reasonable answers; and describing the exponent and the base in a number expressed in exponential notation. The items was distributed into three difficulty levels: easy, average, and difficult, with a percentage of 60%, 27%, and 13%, respectively. The distribution of items using the Table of Specifications (TOS) can be seen Appendix D.

Validation of Instrument

The Research Questionnaire was validated by the Center for Research and Development of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College. All the necessary information in the instrument was checked and approved before it was administered to the respondents. The questionnaire was the instrument used by the researcher in the study to gather the necessary data and information from the respondents.

The Master Teacher validated questionnaire has 30 items. The correlations between factors of the instrument, show relationship and dependence between them, indicating the validity of the questionnaire. The statistical results validated the questionnaire have been significant, allowing to proposed this experience as a starting point to implement further studies about the development of research skills in Manggahan Elementary School pupil's from other areas of knowledge.

Research Procedure

The researcher conducted a screening of 20 pupils were carefully selected for the experimental group. Another 20 pupils also were carefully selected for control group. Purposive selection was used in this study. The researcher submitted the request to conduct the study through the Dean of the Graduate School and after the approval initial preparation on the preparation of the instrument tool was submitted for approval to be piloted securing the reliability of the test. The researcher then ask permission from the Graduate School of Dr. Carlos S. Lanting College to conduct the study at MES which was forwarded to the school head for the approval to conduct the study in the said school. The was sent to the office of the District Supervisor and another to the office of the Division Superintendent for permission and notice.

This was done by sending a formal memorandum together with the information letter to the school where there commended researcher was assigned. This process led to the formal conduct of the study .Then the study was introduced to the respondents. A pretest would be conducted and after that the experimental group would continue with the program for a month and a post test would then be again given to both groups which would later on be tabulated and computed for statistical interpretation.

Data Gathering Technique

In this study, the researcher used a teacher-made test as an instrument: pretest and post-test

Pretest

The data was collected through a pre-test and administered to experimental and control groups. The pre-test was held in both classes to measure the learner's mastery of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns before the experimental research study or before teaching by utilizing the Math Apps-Aided instructions for the experimental group and the conventional way of teaching mathematics for the control group moreover, the researcher gave enrichment activities to both experimental and control groups.

Post-test

After the researcher applied the treatment, the post-tests was administered to both experimental and control groups using the same content as the pre-test but in a different order. Administering a Post-test with the purpose of measuring the performance level of the learners in number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns.

Learning Gains

In this study, the researcher want to know the effectiveness of the Math Apps-Aided instructions compared to the convention teaching method. Thus, the learning gains were computed for both experimental and control groups. This is to determine and measure the learning growths or the effectiveness of the treatment.

Ethical Consideration

Considering the fact that the research participants are human beings, strict ethical considerations were observed; the researcher ensured that the students' health and rights were not harmed. The primary concern of the researcher should be the safety of the research participant. This is accomplished by carefully considering the risk/benefit ratio, using all available information to make an appropriate assessment and continually monitoring the research as it proceeds. Since this study is harmless in nature, there is no problem in regards to possible harm.

Autonomy involves self-determination and freedom. Autonomy is the right of everyone to cover identity and to generate personal decisions independently. Each and every pupil has the right to refuse intervention if it is against their would. Allowing the sample whether to accept or refuse the intervention with consideration (Beauchamp, 2001). Since the intervention is purely harmless and educational in nature, there is no problem Of invoking autonomy.

Confidentiality safeguards the trust of clients that information learned in the context of a professional relationship is shared outside the educational institution with the client's permission or as legally required. *Right of anonymity* must also be respected if the client invokes such right. The researcher must enumerate how privacy and confidentiality concerns would be approached. The researcher must be sensitive to not only how information is protected from unauthorized observation, but also if and how participants are to be notified of any unforeseen findings from the research that they may or may not want to know.

The *principle of beneficence* addresses deeds of mercy kindness and charity. Beneficence means taking action to promote the welfare of other people, the manipulation seeks the benefit of the use of math songs and video clips should be explained to the participants and discusses its possible effect. This study on the effectiveness of math app-aides instruction is beneficial in nature.

Non-malifcence means to do no harm and is considered to be an over-riding principle for everyone who undertakes any experimental research study (Munson, 2004). It is the responsibility of the researchers for whatever happens to the research participant after the initial intervention so we must be cautious not to harm the research participant or cause anything that will degrade the subjects' well-being.

Honesty and integrity are also two important terms. The researcher maintains the highest level of honesty and integrity. Imaginary research and hocus-focus method have no part in this study.

Statistical Treatment

Data was gathered from the respondents would be properly tallied, tabulated, interpreted and analyzed.

The **learning gains** was the measure of academic growth or improvement a student. To compute the learning gains, we utilized the normalized gain (Hake, 1998)

The **Levene's test for homogeneity** was used to know if the data are homogeneous or heterogeneous. It is used to show if two or more groups of sample data from populations with the same variations. It is also used to determine whether several variations of the data in the populations were the same or not. the test for homogeneity is used prior to independent t-test.

The **independent t-test**, also called the two sample t-test, is parametric test that determines whether there is a statistically significant difference between the means of two unrelated groups. In this study, independent t-test was used to determine if the significant difference between

- ✓ pre-test scores of the experimental and control group and
- ✓ post-test scores of the experimental and control group.

The **dependent t-test**, also called the paired t-test, compares the means of two related groups to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between these means. In this study, the dependent t-test was used to determine if the difference between the:

- ✓ pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group; and pre-test and post-test scores of the control group

Results and Discussions

Descriptive Analysis

The data of this study was quantitative data taken by pre-test and post-test. The pre-test was conducted during the first meeting by the researcher. Those tests were given to both experimental class and controlled class. The pre-test provides information about both class's mathematical skills (30 items) in terms of number sense (8 items), basic operation (6 items), problem solving (8 items), and mathematical pattern (8 items). The post-test was administered then to both classes after the experimental class got the treatments and the control class taught the conventional teaching.

In this study, the experimental class was the students of the researcher. The pre-test and post-test results for the experimental class and the control class are shown in Tables 1 and 2. Moreover, the following tables show the pre-test and post-test scores for each mathematical skill: number sense, basic operations, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns.

Table 1. Pre-test mean score of experimental and control class

	Experimental Class			Control Class		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
Number sense	20	2.35	1.35	20	2.35	.99
Basic Operation	20	1.60	1.19	20	2.15	.99
Problem solving	20	2.15	1.23	20	2.55	1.32
Mathematical patterns	20	1.90	1.77	20	2.30	1.38
OVERALL Pre-test Score	20	8.00	3.46	20	9.35	2.85

Table 1 represents the experimental and controlled classes' mean pre-test. As presented, the mean score of the experimental class for number sense is 2.35 with a standard deviation of 1.35, for basic operation is 2.15 with a standard deviation of 1.23, for problem-solving is 2.15 with a standard deviation of 1.23, and for mathematical patterns is 1.90 with a standard deviation of 1.90. Additionally, the overall mean pre-test for the experimental class is 8.00, with a standard deviation of 3.46.

Moreover, the mean score of the controlled class for number sense is 2.35 with a standard deviation of 0.99, for basic operation is 2.15 with a standard deviation of 0.99, for problem-solving is 2.55 with a standard deviation of 1.32, and for mathematical patterns is 2.30 with a standard deviation of 1.38. Overall, the control class's mean pre-test is 9.35, with a standard deviation of 2.85.

Table 2. Posttest mean score of experimental and control class

	Experimental Class			Control Class		
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD
Number sense	20	6.70	1.56	20	4.00	1.59
Basic Operation	20	4.60	1.19	20	2.30	1.34
Problem solving	20	6.30	1.45	20	2.80	1.44
Mathematical patterns	20	7.05	1.28	20	3.00	1.52
OVERALL Post-test Score	20	24.65	4.09	20	12.10	3.16

The mean post-test for the experimental class and controlled class are presented in Table 2. Based on the results presented, the mean post-test for number sense is 6.70 with a standard deviation of 1.56, for basic operation is 4.60 with a standard deviation of 1.19, for problem-solving is 6.30 with a standard deviation of 1.45, and for mathematical patterns is 7.05 with a standard deviation of 1.28. Additionally, the overall mean pre-test for the experimental class is 24.65, with a standard deviation of 4.06.

Furthermore, the mean post-test score for the controlled class for number sense is 4.00 with a standard deviation of 1.59, for basic operation is 2.30 with a standard deviation of 1.34, for problem-solving is 2.80 with a standard deviation of 1.44, and for mathematical patterns is 3.00 with a standard deviation of 1.52. Overall, the control class's mean post-test is 9.35, with a standard deviation of 2.85.

It can be seen from the results that both classes have different results. In addition, we can conclude that both classes' mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns was higher than the pre-test results by using Math Apps Aided Instruction for the experimental class and the conventional method for the controlled class.

Testing of Hypotheses

Normality Test

The test for normality is the preliminary analysis used before testing hypotheses. It was intended to know if the collected data was distributed normally or not. The data was normal when the significant value is bigger than 0.05 ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$) and when the significant value is less than .05 ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$) the distribution data was not normal. The results is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Tests of Normality

Class		Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Pre-test	Experimental Class	.182	20	.082	.941	20	.255
	Control Class	.168	20	.141	.946	20	.309
Post-test	Experimental Class	.156	20	.200*	.938	20	.216
	Control Class	.114	20	.200*	.964	20	.623

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Based on the results shown in Table 3, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk test showed the significance or the p-values (Sig.) were above .05 level of significance. Therefore, the distribution of the pre-test score and post-test score was normally distributed .

Test for difference between the pre-test scores of the experimental and control group in terms of their Mathematical skills.

In this section, a test for significant difference between the pre-test scores of the experimental class and the control class using an independent t-test. The results are shown in Table 4a and Table 4b.

Table 4a (group statistics) shows the two classes, the experimental class, and the control class. Also, the mean, standard deviation, and standard error are shown for each class in terms of the mathematical skills, namely, number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns.

Table 4a. Group Statistics of Pre-test Scores

Class		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number sense	Experimental Class	20	2.35	1.35	0.30
	Control Class	20	2.35	0.99	0.22
Basic Operation	Experimental Class	20	1.60	1.19	0.27
	Control Class	20	2.15	0.99	0.22
Problem solving	Experimental Class	20	2.15	1.23	0.27
	Control Class	20	2.55	1.32	0.29
Mathematical patterns	Experimental Class	20	1.90	1.77	0.40
	Control Class	20	2.30	1.38	0.31
OVERALL Pre-test Score	Experimental Class	20	8.00	3.46	0.77
	Control Class	20	9.35	2.85	0.64

Based on the results presented in Table 4b using Levene's test for homogeneity, it was known that the p-value (sig.) of the variances score for number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, mathematical patterns, and overall was .085, .595, .507, .248, and .576, respectively. It means that the significance value was higher than .05 level of significance. It is assumed that the variances of the experimental class and the control class were homogeneous or equal variances. Because the data was homogeneous, an independent sample t-test was utilized.

Table 4b. Independent Samples Test of Pre-test Scores

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Diff.
Number sense	Equal variances assumed	3.135	.085	0.000	38	1.000	0.00000	.37381
	Equal variances not assumed			0.000	34.837	1.000	0.00000	.37381
Basic Operation	Equal variances assumed	.287	.595	-1.592	38	.120	-.55000	.34546
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.592	36.783	.120	-.55000	.34546
Problem solving	Equal variances assumed	.450	.507	-.994	38	.326	-.40000	.40230
	Equal variances not assumed			-.994	37.806	.326	-.40000	.40230
Mathematical patterns	Equal variances assumed	1.379	.248	-.796	38	.431	-.40000	.50262
	Equal variances not assumed			-.796	35.834	.431	-.40000	.50262
OVERALL Pre-test Score	Equal variances assumed	.319	.576	-1.345	38	.186	-1.35000	1.00335
	Equal variances not assumed			-1.345	36.649	.187	-1.35000	1.00335

As presented in Table 4b, it can be seen that the p-value is greater than the .05 level of significance for number sense ($t_{df=38}=0.000$, $p\text{-value}=1.000$), basic operation ($t_{df=38}=-1.592$, $p\text{-value}=.120$), problem-solving ($t_{df=38}=-.994$, $p\text{-value}=.326$), and mathematical patterns ($t_{df=38}=-.796$, $p\text{-value}=.431$). It means that the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference between the experimental class and the control class. Moreover, the results shows that the p-value of the overall pre-test is greater than the .05 level of significance, $t_{df=38}=-1.345$, $p\text{-value}=.186$. It means that the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference between the experimental class ($M=8.00$, $SD=3.46$) and the control class ($M=9.35$, $SD=2.85$). Hence, the experimental class and control class conditions, in the beginning, are the same, which means that the experimental class's mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns are the same as the control class.

Test for difference between the pre-test scores and the post-test scores for the experimental and control groups.

In this section, a dependent t-test or a paired sample t-test was utilized to determine if the difference between the means of pre-test scores and the post-test scores is statistically significant. And to ensure the effectiveness of the Math Aid Instructions in improving students' mathematical skills. The result is shown in Table 5a and 5b for the experimental class and Tables 6a and 6b for the controlled class.

Experimental Class

Table 5a shows the paired sample statistics for the experimental class. It shows the means, standard deviation, and standard error of the paired samples for each mathematical skill: number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns. In addition, the overall pre-test score for the experimental group is also presented in table 5a.

Table 5a. Paired Samples Statistics for Experimental Class

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number sense	Experimental Class	2.35	20	1.35	0.30
	Control Class	6.70	20	1.56	0.35
Basic Operation	Experimental Class	1.60	20	1.19	0.27
	Control Class	4.60	20	1.19	0.27
Problem solving	Experimental Class	2.15	20	1.23	0.27
	Control Class	6.30	20	1.45	0.33
Mathematical patterns	Experimental Class	1.90	20	1.77	0.40
	Control Class	7.05	20	1.28	0.29
OVERALL Pretest Score	Experimental Class	8.00	20	3.46	0.77
	Control Class	24.65	20	4.09	0.92

Table 5b. Paired Samples Test for Experimental Class

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Number sense	Pre-test vs Post-test	-4.35	1.81	0.41	-10.722	19	.000
Basic Operation	Pre-test vs Post-test	-3.00	1.45	0.32	-9.247	19	.000
Problem solving	Pre-test vs Post-test	-4.15	1.84	0.41	-10.069	19	.000
Mathematical patterns	Pre-test vs Post-test	-5.15	2.37	0.53	-9.726	19	.000

Posttest Score	Pre-test vs Post-test	-16.65	5.51	1.23	-13.517	19	.000
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The results in Table 5b shows the t statistics and the p-values (Sig.) for the mathematical skill: number sense ($t_{df=19}=-10.722$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), basic operation ($t_{df=19}=-9.247$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), problem-solving ($t_{df=19}=-10.069$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), and mathematical patterns ($t_{df=19}=-9.726$, $p\text{-value}=.000$). The p-values are less than the set significance level of .05. In addition, the p-value of the overall pre-test score is less than the .05 level of significance, $t_{df=19}=-14.07$, $p\text{-value}=.000$. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis and concluding that there is a statistically significant difference in the experimental class's pre-test and post-test scores.

Furthermore, the negative which appears in t-statistics means that the mean before the intervention is lower than after the intervention, meaning that the student's score before being taught using a Math Apps Aided Instruction is low. Thus, we can conclude that the mathematical skills (in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns) of the experimental significantly increase when Math Apps Aided Instruction is applied

Controlled Class

Table 6a shows the paired sample statistics for the controlled class. It shows the means, standard deviation, and standard error of the paired samples for each mathematical skill: number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns. In addition, the overall pre-test score for the experimental group is also presented in table 6a.

Table 6a. Paired Samples Statistics for Control Class

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number sense	Experimental Class	2.35	20	.99	.22
	Control Class	4.00	20	1.59	.36
Basic Operation	Experimental Class	2.15	20	.99	.22
	Control Class	2.30	20	1.34	.30
Problem solving	Experimental Class	2.55	20	1.32	.29
	Control Class	2.80	20	1.44	.32
Mathematical patterns	Experimental Class	2.30	20	1.38	.31
	Control Class	3.00	20	1.52	.34
Pretest Score	Experimental Class	9.35	20	2.85	.64
	Control Class	12.10	20	3.16	.71

Table 6b. Paired Samples Test for Control Class

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Number sense	Pre-test vs Post-test	-1.65	1.31	0.29	-5.638	19	.000
Basic Operation	Pre-test vs Post-test	-0.15	1.14	0.25	-.590	19	.562
Problem solving	Pre-test vs Post-test	-0.25	1.62	0.36	-.691	19	.498
Mathematical patterns	Pre-test vs Post-test	-0.70	1.69	0.38	-1.853	19	.079
Posttest Score	Pre-test vs Post-test	-2.75	2.92	0.65	-4.215	19	.000

As presented in table 6b, the results shows the t statistics and the p-values (Sig.) for the mathematical skill: number sense ($t_{df=19}=-5.638$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), basic operation ($t_{df=19}=-0.890$, $p\text{-value}=.562$), problem-solving ($t_{df=19}=-0.691$, $p\text{-value}=.498$), and mathematical patterns ($t_{df=19}=-1.853$, $p\text{-value}=.079$). As indicated, the p-values of the mathematical skills basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns are greater than the set significance level of .05. Thus, failing to reject the null hypotheses indicates no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the controlled group in terms of basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns. In contrast, the p-value of the number sense is less than .05 level of significance. Rejecting the null hypothesis, indicating a significant difference in the mathematical skills in terms of number sense. In addition, the p-value of the overall pre-test score is less than the .05 level of significance, $t_{df=19}=-4.215$, $p\text{-value}=.000$. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis and concluding that there is a statistically significant difference in the controlled class's pre-test and post-test scores.

Furthermore, the negative which appears in t-statistics of the overall means that the mean before the intervention is lower than after using the conventional teaching method. This means that the student's score is low before being taught using the conventional method. Although the mathematical skills in terms of basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns do not improve, the overall mathematical skills of the controlled class significantly increase applying the conventional teaching method.

Test for difference between the post-test scores of the experimental and control group in terms of their Mathematical skills

Finally, a test for the significant difference in the post-test score of the experimental class and control class is presented in Tables 7a and 7b. This is to know if the condition of the classes after giving the intervention to the experimental class are the same with the control class. Table 7a (group statistics) shows the mean, standard deviation, and standard error of the post-test score of both classes.

Table 7a. Group Statistics of Post-test scores.

Class		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number sense	Experimental Class	20	6.70	1.56	0.35
	Control Class	20	4.00	1.59	0.36
Basic Operation	Experimental Class	20	4.60	1.19	0.27
	Control Class	20	2.30	1.34	0.30
Problem solving	Experimental Class	20	6.30	1.45	0.33
	Control Class	20	2.80	1.44	0.32
Mathematical patterns	Experimental Class	20	7.05	1.28	0.29
	Control Class	20	3.00	1.52	0.34
Posttest Score	Experimental Class	20	24.65	4.09	0.92
	Control Class	20	12.10	3.16	0.71

Based on the results presented in Table 7b using Levene's test for homogeneity, it was known that the p-value (sig.) of the variances score for number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, mathematical patterns, and overall was .759, .725, .940, .364, and .109, respectively. Indicating that the significance value is higher than .05 level of significance. It is assumed that the experimental class and the control class variances were homogeneous or equal variances. Because the data was homogeneous, an independent sample t-test was utilized.

Table 7b. Difference between the post-test scores of the experimental and control group in terms of their Mathematical skills

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Number sense	Equal variances assumed	.096	.759	5.423	38	.000	2.700	0.498
	Equal variances not assumed			5.423	37.986	.000	2.700	0.498
Basic Operation	Equal variances assumed	.126	.725	5.741	38	.000	2.300	0.401
	Equal variances not assumed			5.741	37.449	.000	2.300	0.401
Problem solving	Equal variances assumed	.006	.940	7.657	38	.000	3.500	0.457
	Equal variances not assumed			7.657	37.994	.000	3.500	0.457
Mathematical patterns	Equal variances assumed	.845	.364	9.119	38	.000	4.050	0.444
	Equal variances not assumed			9.119	36.882	.000	4.050	0.444
Posttest Score	Equal variances assumed	2.701	.109	10.851	38	.000	12.550	1.157
	Equal variances not assumed			10.851	35.709	.000	12.550	1.157

As presented in Table 7b, it can be seen that the p-value is less than the .05 level of significance for number sense ($t_{df=38}=5.423$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), basic operation ($t_{df=38}=5.741$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), problem-solving ($t_{df=38}=7.657$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), and mathematical patterns ($t_{df=38}=9.119$, $p\text{-value}=.000$). It means that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a statistically significant difference between the post-test score experimental class and the control class. Moreover, the results show that the p-value of the overall pre-test is less than the .05 level of significance, $t_{df=38}=10.851$, $p\text{-value}=.000$. It means that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating no statistically significant difference between the overall post-test score of the experimental class ($M=24.65$, $SD=4.09$) and the control class ($M=12.10$, $SD=3.16$). Hence, the mean post-test score of the experimental class is higher than the mean post-test score of the control class. In other words, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the scores between students taught by using Math Apps Aided Instructions and those taught using the conventional method.

Test for improvement in the mathematical skills of the participants in using Math Apps-Aided Instruction.

In this section, to determine if there is an improvement in the mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns of the participants in using Math Apps Aided Instruction, the learning gains or the normalized gains by Hake (1998) was computed.

Table 8a shows the group statistics of the experimental and controlled classes' learning gains. Results show that the experimental class's mean learning gains are positive, ranging from 67.3% to 81.7%. An

indication that there is an improvement in the students’ mathematical skills in using Math apps Aided Instructions, specifically on number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns. On the other hand, the learning gains of the controlled class are positive for the mathematical skills of number sense (30.0%), basic operation 1.6%, and mathematical patterns (9.2%). However, there is no improvement in mathematical skills in terms of problem-solving since the computed learning gain is -1.2%.

Overall, there is an improvement in the mathematical skills of the participants in using Math Apps-Aided Instructions for the experimental group (g=75.1%, SD=18.4%) and using the conventional method for the controlled group (g=12.9%, SD=11.8%). Hence, both methods effectively improve the mathematical skills of the participants of the study.

Table 8a. Group Statistics for Learning Gains

Class		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Number sense	Experimental Class	20	.776	.252	.056
	Control Class	20	.300	.240	.054
Basic Operation	Experimental Class	20	.673	.241	.054
	Control Class	20	.016	.370	.083
Problem solving	Experimental Class	20	.698	.257	.058
	Control Class	20	-.012	.360	.080
Mathematical patterns	Experimental Class	20	.817	.258	.058
	Control Class	20	.092	.277	.062
Posttest Score	Experimental Class	20	.751	.184	.041
	Control Class	20	.129	.118	.026

The learning gains of the experimental class is compared to the learning gains of the controlled class to determine the effectiveness of the treatment (Math Apps-Aided Instructions). An independent sample t-test was utilized to assess the significance of this difference. This result is shown in Table 8b.

A test for homogeneity was the initial data analysis to determine if the data samples were equal variances or homogenous. As revealed in Table 8b, using Levene’s test for homogeneity, it was known that the p-value (sig.) of the variances score for number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns was .451, .375, .402, and .471, respectively. It means that the significance value was higher than .05 level of significance. It is assumed that the experimental class and the control class variances were homogeneous or equal variances. Because the data was homogeneous, an independent sample t-test was utilized for the mathematical skills of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns. However, the p-value of the overall learning gains using Levene’s test is .003 which is less than the .05 level of significance. Because the data were heterogeneous or unequal variances for overall learning gain, Satterthwaite’s approximate t-test will be calculated.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Number sense	Equal variances assumed	.581	.451	6.116	38	.000	.475	.078

	Equal variances not assumed			6.116	37.903	.000	.475	.078
Basic Operation	Equal variances assumed	.806	.375	6.648	38	.000	.657	.099
	Equal variances not assumed			6.648	32.619	.000	.657	.099
Problem solving	Equal variances assumed	.718	.402	7.173	38	.000	.710	.099
	Equal variances not assumed			7.173	34.416	.000	.710	.099
Mathematical patterns	Equal variances assumed	.531	.471	8.559	38	.000	.725	.085
	Equal variances not assumed			8.559	37.798	.000	.725	.085
Posttest Score	Equal variances assumed	10.453	.003	12.724	38	.000	.622	.049
	Equal variances not assumed			12.724	32.456	.000	.622	.049

As presented in Table 8b, it can be seen that the p-value is less than the .05 level of significance for number sense ($t_{df=38}=6.116$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), basic operation ($t_{df=38}=6.648$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), problem-solving ($t_{df=38}=7.173$, $p\text{-value}=.000$), and mathematical patterns ($t_{df=38}=8.559$, $p\text{-value}=.000$). It means that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a statistically significant difference between the learning gains of the experimental class and the control class. Moreover, the results shows that the p-value of the overall learning gains is less than the .05 level of significance, $t_{df=32.456}=12.724$, $p\text{-value}=.000$. It means that the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a statistically significant difference between the learning gains of the experimental class ($M=8.00$, $SD=3.46$) and the control class ($M=9.35$, $SD=2.85$). Hence, Math Apps-Aided Instructions is more effective than the conventional method of teaching, thus, Math apps-Aided Instructions significantly improves the participants mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns.

Conclusion

Based from the findings in the study, the following are concluded;

1. Both classes' mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns was higher than the pre-test results by using Math Apps Aided Instruction for the experimental class and the conventional method for the controlled class.
2. The experimental class's mathematical skills in terms of number sense, basic operation, problem-solving, and mathematical patterns are the same as the control class.
3. That when Math Apps Aided Instruction is used, the experimental subjects' mathematical abilities (in terms of number sense, fundamental operations, problem solving, and mathematical patterns) significantly improve.

4. There is a significant difference in scores exists between students taught using Math Apps Aided Instructions and those taught using the conventional method.
5. That Math Apps-Aided Instructions is more effective than the conventional method of instruction; consequently, Math Apps-Aided Instructions significantly improves participants' mathematical abilities in terms of number sense, basic operations, problem solving, and mathematical patterns.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. For future researchers and graduate students, this study be conducted in other public or private schools for external validation especially on basic education sector. Its purpose is to determine whether the findings in this study can be generalized among all grade 6 pupils and other levels in elementary education. In this case, replication or secondary analysis can be utilized.
2. It is likewise recommended that the conduct of another study be done on homogeneous sections for experimental group and control group which will use either lowest sections which have low academic performance or highest sections whose pupils for comparison purposes.
3. It is also recommended to expand more on the content of math apps materials in the instruction of Mathematics that can be downloaded in both English and Tagalog from the internet or purchasing children educational learning materials related to mathematics or any subject.
4. More statistical measures are needed to further verify the effectiveness of math apps-aided materials as a instructional strategy in raising the level of interest, enthusiasm and achievement of pupils in mathematics.
5. For teachers in Grade 6 pupils, the researcher highly recommends the use of math apps-aided materials in their teaching to ensure augmented interest, enthusiasm and achievement among Grade 6 pupils in their study of mathematics.
6. For the Department of Education, to institutionalize the use of math apps in the teaching of mathematics among Grade 6 pupils and if possible to all Grade levels in the elementary education.

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